

Conductometric Determination of Gadolinium as Molybdate

Kashi Prasad Srivastava

The reaction between gadolinium and molybdate ions has been followed by means of direct as well as reverse conductometric titrations. The curves, obtained show a sharp break and lend support to the formation of normal gadolinium molybdate molar ratio of gadolinium and molybdate being 2:3. The accuracy and reproducibility of the results has been found to be excellent even at low concentrations. The effect of ethanol on the result has also been investigated.

A number of procedures for the determination of gadolinium are reported in the literature. Hara and West¹ employed high frequency titrations with disodium salt of E.D.T.A. in buffered medium, Monk and Harrington² used microspectrophotometric titrations against disodium salt of E.D.T.A. at 550 m μ using Erichrome Black T as indicator and Garifyanov and Mazitov³ used N.M.R. technique for the micro-determination of gadolinium. Besides, it has been estimated spectroscopically⁴ and spectrophotometrically⁵.

In view of our recent communication on the conductometric determination of Sm³⁺ as molybdate⁶, it was considered of interest to extend similar studies to the determination of gadolinium as molybdate.

EXPERIMENTAL AND RESULTS

Gadolinium oxide (A.R., Atomic Energy Establishment, Trombay) was dissolved in minimum quantity of A.R. nitric acid and evaporated to dryness. The product obtained was purified by recrystallisation from 30% A. R. nitric acid⁷. Gadolinium nitrate obtained

1. R. Hara and P. W. West, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1956, 14, 280.
2. R. G. Monk and J. Harrington, *ibid.*, 1961, 24, 481.
3. N. S. Garifyanov, R. K. Mazitov, *Zh. Analit. Khim.*, 1963, 18, 283.
4. P. W. Selwood, "Ind. Eng. Chem. anal.", Ed 2, 96, 1930;
K. Kimura & Y. Tsunoda, *J. C. S. (Japan)*, 1935, 54, 76.
K. Kimura, *Bull. Chem. Soc. (Japan)*, 1938, 13, 27.
M. Servigne, *Bull. Soc. Chem.*, 1940, 7, 121.
V. A. Fassel, *J. Optical Soc. Am.*, 1949, 39, 187.
T. Moeller & J. C. Brantley, *Anal. Chem.*, 1950, 22, 433.
J. A. Norris & G. E. Pepper, *Anal. Chem.*, 1952, 24, 1399.
R. N. Kniseley, V. A., *Spectrochem Acta*, 1958, 12, 332.
Fassel B. B. Quinney, C. Tremmel, W. A. Gordon & W. J. Hayles, S. Robt & W. Rinchart *Anal. Chem.* 1954, 26, 1820.
5. G. V. Banks & D. W. Klingmann, *Anal. Chem. Acta.*, 1956, 15, 356.
B. Budecinsky and A. Bezdchova, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1963, 196, 172.
Shooshibata, *Anal. Chem. Asia.*, 1963, 28, 388.
G. Brunisholtz and R. Cation, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1956, 39, 3136.
6. K. P. Srivastava *Proc. Inst. Chem. (India)*, 1965, 37, 9.
7. Hopkins, B. S., "Chapters in the Chemistry of Less Familiar Elements", Chapter 6, 1939, p. 18.

was dissolved in conductivity water and recrystallised thrice. Sodium molybdate (E. Merck extra pure quality) and gadolinium nitrate were dissolved separately in conductivity water. In these solutions molybdenum was estimated by the usual gravimetric procedure and gadolinium as Gd_2O_3 . Solutions of lower concentrations were obtained by appropriate dilutions.

Titrations were carried out at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ C$ in a 100 ml pyrex beaker using mains operated Philips conductivity bridge P.R. 9500 and a dip cell 9510 with a cell constant 1.46. Readings were recorded in 'ohms' at the output frequency of 50 cycles/sec. The reciprocal of the resistance (conductance) was plotted against the volume in ml of the titrant added.

When the titration of gadolinium nitrate against sodium molybdate was carried out in purely aqueous medium, low results were obtained which improved on addition of ethanol. A number of titrations were, therefore, carried out at different ethanol concentrations ranging from 0.16% of which 2.5–5.6% gave the best results.

In direct titrations different volumes of gadolinium nitrate solution with an overall 2.5% ethanol was taken in the cell and diluted to 70 ml with conductivity water. It was placed on the magnetic stirrer, the electrodes dipped properly in the solution and initial resistance recorded. Sodium molybdate was then added in small amount from a micro-burette, the mixture stirred well and the resistance recorded after five minutes of each addition of the titrant. End-point was obtained graphically by plotting volume of the titrant against the conductance (cf. Fig. 2, Table 2A).

FIG. 1

TABLE I

Effect of Ethanol

No.	Molarity of titrate	Ethanol conc. %	Amount of Gd+++ in mg.		Difference in mg.
			Taken	Found	
			Volume of titration mixture	=70 ml	
Temperature	=30±0.5°C				
Concentration of titrant	=0.1027M				
1.	1.126×10 ⁻³	0 or aqueous	12.37	12.26	+0.11
2.	1.126×10 ⁻³	2.50	12.37	12.37	0.00
3.	1.126×10 ⁻³	5.00	12.37	12.37	0.00
4.	1.126×10 ⁻³	7.50	12.37	12.31	+0.06
5.	1.126×10 ⁻³	10.00	12.37	12.26	+0.11

TABLE 2A

Direct conductometric titration

No.	Molarity of titrate, M.	Amount of Gadolinium in mg.		Difference in mg.
		Taken	Found	
		Volume of titration mixture	=70 ml	
Temperature	=30±0.5°C			
Concentration of titrant	=0.1027M			
Ethanol concentration	=2.50%			
1.	0.4504×10 ⁻³	4.948	4.894	+0.054
2.	0.6756×10 ⁻³	7.408	7.408	0.000
3.	0.9008×10 ⁻³	9.896	9.949	-0.053
4.	1.126×10 ⁻³	12.370	12.370	0.000
5.	1.3512×10 ⁻³	14.844	14.790	+0.054

TABLE 2B

Reverse conductometric titration

No.	Molarity of titration M.	Amount of Gadolinium in mg.		Difference in mg.
		Taken	Found	
		Volume of titration mixture	=70 ml	
Temperature	=30±0.5°C			
Concentration of titrant	=0.07877M			
Ethanol concentration	=2.4%			
1.	0.8808×10 ⁻³	6.375	6.052	+0.323
2.	1.1744×10 ⁻³	8.600	7.854	+0.746
3.	1.4680×10 ⁻³	10.740	8.262	+2.478

In case of reverse titrations sodium molybdate solution with 2.5% ethanol concentration was taken in the cell and titrated against gadolinium nitrate, other procedures being the same as in the case of direct titrations (cf. Fig. 3, Table 2B).

FIG. 2

DISCUSSION

It is evident from the conductometric titration curves that one sharp point of intersection is obtained corresponding to the formation of gadolinium molybdate in the molar ratio of 2:3 of Gd : Mo and the reaction may be represented as :

In direct titrations as the sodium molybdate solution was added to the gadolinium nitrate solution, there was practically no change in the conductance up to the equivalence point. In the post-equivalence region a rapid increase in the conductance was observed due to Na_2MoO_4 being added the excess (cf. Fig. 2). In reverse titrations when $\text{Gd}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ was added to Na_2MoO_4 solution at 2.5% alcoholic concentration, the curves were quite smooth but premature end-points were obtained. It seems probable that molybdate ions are absorbed on the gadolinium molybdate formed as has already been observed in the case of Samarium molybdate 6 (cf. Fig 3). The presence of ethanol improves the end-point slightly as it reduces the solubility of the precipitated compound.

Thus the present investigation confirms the formation of normal gadolinium molybdate and the conductometric method is much more convenient than other methods used for the micro-determination of gadolinium. The accuracy and reproducibility of the titra-

FIG. 3

tion has been found to be excellent even at low concentration of gadolinium ($0.4504 \times 10^{-3}M$). Cations which form precipitate with sodium molybdate and anions, which react with gadolinium e.g. selenite, tellurite, vanadate tungstate, chromate interfere and must be absent.

My grateful thanks are due to Dr. Sarju Prasad, D.Sc., Actg. Head of the Department of Chemistry, B.H.U. for suggesting the problem and helpful guidance and to the authorities of Birla Institute of Technology & Science, Pilani and the Banaras Hindu University for providing facilities for the work. My thanks are also due to the University Grants Commission and Council of Scientific and Industrial Research for contingency grants.